

1 *Devyāmata* chapter 83: the excavation and the laying of the cords in the cardinal directions (diksūtras) edition

Devyāmata, khāto diksūtrāvarāṇalakṣaṇaṃ trayāśītimapaṭalaḥ, edition.

N 87r, line 4; M Mf60v, line 4; Wf67v, line 3

- 83.1 athādaḥ saviśeṣeṇa vāstunaḥ khātalakṣaṇaṃ
brahmasūtrāvātāraṃ ca khātādhasṭād ihocyate
- 83.2 jagatimānavistīrṇaṃ rathakāvyadhikaṃ samam
khātavyaṃ salilaṃ khātaṃ prāgrīvamaṇḍapānvitam
- 83.3 śaṅkhaṃ śuklapravalāni muktā halaṃ ca kāñcanaṃ
rājataṃ maṇiratnāni māṇḍukaḥ kacchapo 'thavā
- 83.4 khanyamāne yadā khāte labhyante vāstumadhyataḥ
sarvadā kāmadaḥ puṃsāṃ dr̥ṣṭvā tān abhinandayet
- 83.5 tāvat khātaṃ tu khātavyaṃ yāvat toyaśīlāntagam
khātaṃ samatalaṃ kuryāt samantāt paridhisamam
- 83.6 khātādhasṭāt tato bhūmiṃ samantāt sutalāṃ samām
kṛtvā samyak tatas tatra diksūtram avatārayet
- 83.7 agrataḥ pṛṣṭhatas caiva khātasyaivordhvato bahiḥ
sūtraṃ prasārayet tāvad yāvat syān matsyayor bahiḥ
- 83.8 matsyamadhye tataḥ sthāpya kṛtvā sutānitaṃ bahiḥ
nirūpya suciraṃ kṛtvā lambanaṃ tatra lambayet

Wf68r

N f87v

Mf61r

Ω = NM(→W)

1b vāstunaḥ] N; vāstuna M 2a vistīrṇaṃ] N; vistīrṇa M
2c khātavyaṃ] N; khātavya M 3a śaṅkhaṃ] em.; śaṅkha N; śaṅkha M
3c rājataṃ] M; rājata N 4c kāmadaḥ] em.; kāmada NM • puṃsāṃ] N; puṃsā M
4d dr̥ṣṭvā tān abhinandayet] em.; dr̥ṣṭvātāṃnabhinandayet N; dr̥ṣṭātonnavinandayet M
5a tāvat] N; tāva M • khātavyaṃ] N; khātavya M 6a bhūmiṃ] N; bhūmi M
6b samantāt] N; samantā M • talāṃ] N; talāṃ M 7a agrataḥ] N; agrata M
7b bahiḥ] N; bahi M 7c prasārayet] em.; prasāraye NM 7d bahiḥ] N; bahi M
8b sutānitaṃ] N; sutānita M

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83.9 caturaśrāḥ samā bhadraś catasro dikchilās tataḥ
khātādhasṭān nyased yāvac caturdikṣu vicakṣaṇaḥ

83.10 khātasya bhūgataḥ kāryo lambano madhyasaṃsthitāḥ
madhye ca bhūsamā kāryā brahmasthānaprasādhitā

83.11 evaṃ vai dikchilānyāsaṃ kṛtvā khātatale budhaḥ
lambanena tato vidvān diksūtram avatārayet

83.12 ubhayamatsyagaṃ sūtraṃ yat tat khāte paristhitam
lambanaṃ lambayet tatra ubhayor antayor budhaḥ

83.13 tāvat tat lambayed yatnād yāvac chilāgrasaṃsthitāḥ
lambanāgrasthitāṃ yatra śilāṃ vai tatra lāñchayet

83.14 lāñchanadvayamadyena diksūtraṃ samprasārayet
tataḥ sutānitaṃ kṛtvā sūtram āsphālayed guruḥ

Wf68v

83.15 evaṃ pūrvāparaṃ sūtraṃ dvitīyaṃ dakṣiṇottaram
tataḥ prasārayet samyak sūtramārgaṃ śilāntaram

83.16 evaṃ sūtradvayaṃ yatnād adhasṭād avatārayet
khātādhasṭāt tato vidvān prāsādaṃ samprasādhayet

Ω = NM(→W)

- 9a aśrāḥ] em.; aśrā NM • bhadraś] em.; bhadrā NM 9b catasro] em.; cataśro NM
• dikchilās tataḥ] em.; dikchilāmstataḥ N; dikchilānukaḥ M
10a kāryo] N; kāryā M 10b lambano] N; lambana M 11a nyāsaṃ] N; nyāsa M
11b tale] M; tala N 12b tat] M; taṃ N 13a tat] em.; taṃ NM
13b saṃsthitāḥ] N; saṃsthitām M
13c lambanāgrasthitāṃ] em.; lambanāgrasthi[*] N; lambanāgraśchiraṃ M
13d śilāṃ] M; śilāṃ N • tatra] N; yatra M 14a dvayamadhyena] N; dvitayamadhye M
14d āsphālayed] N; āsphāyed M 15b dvitīyaṃ] em.; dvitīyā NM
15c prasārayet] N; prasāraye M 15d sūtramārgaṃ] em.; sūtramārga N; sūtramārga M
16c khātādhasṭāt] N; khātādhasṭā M
16d samprasādhayet] em.; saṃprasāradhayet N; saṃprasārayet M

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83.17 athavā khātamadhye tu sūtramārgeṇa śāstravit
yat tat pūrvāparaṃ sūtraṃ madhye ca tantuṃ lāñchayet

Mf61v

83.18 pūrvatraivāparaṃ bhāgaṃ tasmin samsthāpya lāñchayet
tato matsyadvayaṃ kāryaṃ pūrvavad dakṣiṇottaram

83.19 ubhayor matsyayor madhye sūtraṃ prasārayet tataḥ
ubhayaśilāgataṃ kṛtvā sūtraṃ āsphālayed guruḥ

83.20 tataś ca sūtrasampātaḥ khātamadhye tu yo bhavet
brahmasthānaṃ tu tat proktaṃ tasmād vāstu prasādhayet

83.21 prāsādavistarārdhena sūtraṃ samgrhya yatnataḥ
pūrvavat sūtramārgeṇa prāsādaṃ sūtrayet tataḥ

83.22 brahmasthāne tu samsthāpya caturdikṣu vicakṣaṇaḥ
lāñchayet sūtramārgaṃ tu tataḥ karṇān prasādhayet

83.23 evaṃ susūtritaṃ kṛtvā prāsādaṃ sarvataḥ samaḥ
vidikṣu sūtramārgeṇa śilānyāsaṃ samārabhet

Wf69r

iti khāto diksūtrāvaraṇalakṣaṇaṃ trayāśītimapaṭalaḥ

N is illegible after verse 23.

Ω = NM(→W)

17d tantuṃ] em.; taṃtu N; tuntu M • lāñchayet] N; lācchayet M

18c kāryaṃ] N; kāryā M 19b sūtraṃ] M; sūtra N 19c ubhaya] N; ubhayā M

19d guruḥ] N; gurum M 20a sūtra] N; sūtraṃ M

20c proktaṃ] N; prokta M 20d tasmād] N; tasmātād M

• prasādhayet] N; pr[[ā]]asādhayet M 21a prāsāda] N; prāsārdhā M

21b sūtraṃ] N; sūtra M 22d karṇān] em.; karṇā N; karṇa M

23a susūtritaṃ] N; susūtitāṃ M 23b samaḥ] N; samaṃ M

23c vidikṣu] M; vidukṣu N • sūtra] N; sūtraṃ M

23d śilānyāsaṃ] N; śilāsyāsaṃ M after 23 iti khāto diksūtrāvaraṇalakṣaṇaṃ

trayāśītimapaṭalaḥ] em.; itidevyāmatekhātodiksūtrāvaraṇalakṣaṇaṃtrayāśītimapaṭalaḥ M